

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MENTAL DEVELOPMENT AND EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The article reveals the interaction of mental development and education, in these social relations a person as a member of society, as a representative of a certain class, a particular social group and, finally, as an active member of certain communities with different levels of organization and organization. Purposeful education and upbringing are not only the conditions for the manifestation of what has been given since time immemorial, genetically fixed, but also constitute the mental characteristics of a person.*

Key words: *mental development, education, social attitude, personality, active member of society, upbringing and education, genetics, factor, active being.*

СВЯЗЬ ПСИХИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

Аннотация. *В статье раскрывается взаимодействие психического развития и образования, в этих социальных отношениях человек как член общества, как представитель определенного класса, определенной социальной группы и, наконец, как активный член определенных общностей с разным уровнем организации и устройства.*

Целенаправленное образование и воспитание являются не только условиями проявления того, что дано с незапамятных времен, генетически закреплено, но и составляют психические особенности человека.

Ключевые слова: *психическое развитие, образование, социальная установка, личность, активный член общества, воспитание и образование, генетика, фактор, активное существо.*

INTRODUCTION

Since the Republic of Uzbekistan stabilizes its independence on a global scale from year to year, its future depends on how educated, knowledgeable, spiritually mature people the current generation will become. In this place, the role of the science of psychology, which studies the laws of the human psyche, is extremely important. In order to further increase the effectiveness of education in the formation of a mature person as a full-fledged, active personality, it is very necessary for our society to have the right direction in the science of psychology and its practice.

The science of psychology, relying on modern theory, explains the composition of the human personality, based on the data that it mainly depends on the influence of three factors. The first of them is the influence of the external social environment in which a person is born and

grows up, the second is the influence of education and upbringing, regularly given to a person over a long period of time, and the third is the effect of genetic features that are given to a person from birth, ready.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

It is known that each person is unique, is in a social environment that is definitely not duplicated in others. It grows and develops in specific social relations, i.e. in a certain family, community and society, among people. A person participates in these social relations as a member of society, as a representative of a certain class, a particular social group and, finally, as an active member of certain communities with different levels of organization and organization. The essence of a person is social by nature. The sources of development of all mental properties and creative activity of a person are in the social environment surrounding him, in society. A person's personality is causally related and is determined by his social life. Manna in this sense is the process of acquiring social experience that occurs in relationships with people. As a result, a person's mental characteristics, moral qualities, character, volitional qualities, interests, beliefs and worldview are formed.

The environment, education and training aimed at a specific goal are not only the conditions for the manifestation of something genetically determined since time immemorial, but also form the composition of a person's mental characteristics. In this regard, first of all, it should be noted that a person is not a passive object under the influence of the environment, but an active being. Therefore, it is not the external conditions of life, external influences that determine the psyche of a person, but the personality itself determines through its interaction with the environment, through its activity in the environment. Therefore, it is appropriate to talk not about the influence of the environment, but about the active interaction of a person with the environment. Secondly, the development of the psyche ultimately depends on external conditions and external influences. But this development cannot be directly derived from external conditions and external circumstances. These conditions and situations are always influenced by a person's life experience, his personality, individual psychological characteristics and mental image. Manna in this sense is under the indirect influence of internal conditions, which include the unique psyche and personality of a person.

Thirdly, a person as an active being can consciously change his personality, that is, engage in self-education. But this process does not occur separately from the environment, but in harmony with the environment and in interaction with the environment. Although natural characteristics are not the driving force of development, they influence the mental development of a person. Firstly, natural characteristics determine different ways and methods of developing mental characteristics.

The characteristics of the human nervous system do not in themselves determine any mental characteristics of a person. No normal child is brave or timid, willing or unwilling. A person is not born hard-working or lazy, disciplined or undisciplined. If an educational network is organized, then all socially valuable character traits can be formed on the basis of any type of nervous system. For example, perseverance and self-control should and can be cultivated in children with a tense type of nervous system or in children with a calm type of nervous system.

However, raising children in the first case will be more difficult than in the second. In both cases, the ways and methods of cultivating the necessary qualities are different.

Secondly, natural characteristics can also influence the level of a person's achievements in a certain area. For example, there are innate individual differences in the beginnings of abilities.

Because of this, some people are better than others in terms of the ability to acquire a certain activity. Sometimes, on the contrary, from the point of view of the possibility of acquiring a certain type of activity, they can make them unconscious. When manna is taken in this sense, people do not have the opportunity to equally develop their abilities. Although natural growth has a certain significance for the mental development of students (for example, in the educational process, some students are required to make more efforts than others, some students are made more effort by the teacher, pay attention and spend more time), these buds themselves do not play a decisive role in mental development.

Psychologists of different directions discuss the problem of the interaction of education and upbringing, on the one hand, and development, on the other.

Development is usually understood as both types of events, and these concepts are closely related:

- 1) the brain's own biological, organic development, its anatomical and biological structure;
- 2) mental development as certain stages of growth of mental (intellectual) development, as a special mental maturity.

It goes without saying that mental development is associated with the biological resolution of the brain structure, and this feature must be taken into account in educational work, because education cannot deny the organic formation of the brain. But the

However, it cannot be said that the organic formation of the brain occurs on the basis of its strict biological laws, completely independent of the environment and upbringing. The environment, education and appropriate exercises help to structure the brain organically.

CONCLUSION

Drawing a conclusion from the above, it can be said that the socially organized and active activity of a person (child, student) is the basis, means and condition of his mental development.

It goes without saying that natural, biological capabilities are extremely necessary for the mental development of a person. In order for the mental characteristics of a person to develop normally, a certain level of biological structure, brain and nervous system of a person is necessary.

These natural features are not forces or factors driving mental development, but only initial conditions.

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